

**Digital
Society**

The challenges of a digital society

- A shared response by the Dutch universities -

The challenges
of a digital society

Table of contents

Foreword programme coordinators **3**

Challenges of a digital society and response of Dutch universities **5**

Our partners in researching a digital society **7**

One programme, seven themes **9**

Citizenship & Democracy **10**

Responsible Data Science **13**

Health & Well-Being **16**

Learning & Education **20**

Work & Organisations **22**

Digital Cities & Communities **24**

Safety & Security **26**

Foreword programme coordinators

We are living in a digital society, in which every aspect of our lives is profoundly being affected by the digitalisation of data: how we communicate and socialise; how we work, learn, stay healthy and participate in politics and the economy. This special e-zine is published at the same day that the Dutch universities hold the first Digital Society Conference (27 November 2018). It is still early days as DiSa (DIGITALE SAMENLEVING – Digital Society in Dutch) only started in the spring of 2018, and new researchers are just beginning to take up their posts. DiSa is a joint venture of the fourteen Dutch universities, each of which is investing in one or more of the seven programme lines. It is also an experiment as the VSNU has never before stimulated the universities to work together on a collaborative research agenda.

Dutch universities benefit from an excellent digital infrastructure supporting education and research. The Netherlands has a long-standing culture of openness and collaboration, and is an active promoter of Open Science. Taken together, this means that researchers in the Netherlands are ideally positioned to take on a leadership role in multidisciplinary research for a human-centered digital society.

New digital technologies are being developed very rapidly. Digitalisation and the associated growth of data are affecting all areas of human activity, including politics, work, the economy, and healthcare. Society is changing, sometimes for the better but certainly not always. Digital transformations are characterised by similar narratives of promises and fears, but they share complex questions of, for example, participation, responsibility, security, and surveillance.

No single discipline can address all of the complex socio-technical questions arising from the further development and use of digital technologies and big data. This is why it is important for the universities to work together, across disciplinary boundaries, to develop a shared research agenda that addresses the interests of citizens, politicians, policy makers, and those working in government, civil society and industry. By engaging with a broad range of societal partners we can come up with research that puts societal needs central to further processes of digitalisation and that promotes responsible digitalisation and datafication with people at the centre.

We would like to thank all of the contributors to the conference and the VSNU staff who have worked hard behind the scenes to create the conditions for our fruitful interactions.

We hope you had an enjoyable and productive day at what we hope will be the first of many DiSa conferences. If you have feedback and ideas for future partnerships, collaborations and events, please share them with us.

***Inald Legendijk, Maarten de Rijke and Sally Wyatt
Programme Coordinators, Digital Society***

Challenges of a digital society and response of Dutch universities

We are living in a digital society, in which every aspect of our lives is profoundly being affected by the digitalisation of data: how we communicate and socialise; how we work, learn, stay healthy and participate in politics and the economy.

The societal challenges of a digital society

Digitalisation promises tremendous benefits; for better health, more efficient mobility, efficient energy use, and flourishing companies. Yet it also raises complex challenges: new divides around access to and control of data; what it means to be human when we share the world with sophisticated artificial intelligences; identifying knowledge and truth amongst the deluge of information.

These challenges raise multidisciplinary issues of power, culture, governance and sociality. To address these issues, computer- and data scientists need to work together with social scientists and humanities scholars. In other words, democracy in a digital age is not only of concern to social scientists and humanities scholars; and designing effective algorithms is not the exclusive preserve of computer scientists. The Digital Society programme is a response to these developments.

The response of the Dutch universities

The Association of Universities in the Netherlands (VSNU) has brought together leading researchers from all fourteen universities to work together to address the many pressing questions raised by the emergence of a digital society. Dutch universities benefit from an excellent digital infrastructure supporting education and research. The Netherlands has a long-standing culture of openness and collaboration, and is an active promoter of Open Science. Taken together, this means that researchers in the Netherlands are ideally positioned to take on a leadership role in multidisciplinary research for a human-centred digital society.

The Digital Society programme combines the expertise of over 30 leading professors in their respective fields and supports the Netherlands to develop technologies and applications that serve societal goals and interests, and which can be an example to all.

All Dutch universities have also recruited one or more PhD or postdoc researchers. The Digital Society programme aims to work with multidisciplinary teams composed from the researchers appointed by the programme. The goal of these team is to collaborate on well-defined projects of several months. Project challenges will be defined bottom-up, within and between programme lines, ideally in collaboration with external stakeholders.

Key objectives

- 1** Put societal needs central to further research about processes of digitalisation.
- 2** Promote responsible digitalisation with people at the core.
- 3** Collaborate more with stakeholders.

Our partners in researching a digital society

We cannot address all of the challenges alone, and nor do we want to. We work together with government agencies, private companies, civil society organisations, and with academic colleagues in the Netherlands and beyond. The Digital Society Research Agenda complements and strengthens related NWO programmes, the National Research Agenda (NWA), the Knowledge and Innovation Agendas (KIAs) of the top sectors, and (inter-)national government agendas such as the Cybersecurity Agenda (Min J&V), the Dutch Digitalisation Agenda (NDS), the Digital Government Agenda (DIGibeter) and H2020/FP9.

How we work together

All researchers involved in the Digital Society programme are interested in how culture, society and digital technologies shape and affect each other. We seek to develop a holistic, interdisciplinary understanding of the conditions in which digital technologies are developed and adopted precisely so that different stakeholders can intervene to ensure their optimum use and further development. These are not 'simply' technical problems with technical solutions, but rather complex social, ethical and political questions facing all levels of government, public and private organisations, and people in their everyday lives. For example, a good 'smart city' is one in which citizens, municipalities, infrastructure providers, schools, cultural organisations and employers work together to create a living environment that works for everyone. Our unique collaborations are explicitly aimed at breaking down disciplinary boundaries that hamper addressing the true challenges of the Digital Society.

Some research projects are formulated in response to and discussion with funding agencies, and government organisations. But we also have opportunities to conduct projects that are of crucial importance for and defined by the researchers involved. There are important questions within each of the programme lines, but there are equally important questions facing science and society that cut across the lines. We will organise networking meetings, ranging from small workshops to community meetings, public outreach events and large symposia. The meetings revolve around concrete challenges and results of the programme's three objectives, and are aimed at diverse audiences, and in collaboration with other partners.

How we will enlarge the research community

Over the coming decade, we aim to scale up the programme into a sustainable research effort. Researcher in the Digital Society programme will submit joint multidisciplinary research projects in the context of national NWA and top sector calls, in the European H2020/FP9 program, and other funding opportunities, together with public and private stakeholders from outside academia. Academic staff involved in the programme aims to influence the research agendas of the fourteen universities in order to bring the relevance, urgency and impact of digitalisation, data and algorithms to the attention of academic decision-makers, government and funding bodies.

One programme, seven themes

The Digital Society programme aims to secure the Netherlands a leading international position in the field of human-centred information technology, and to find solutions to global challenges. The universities have identified seven programme lines on which to focus, building on existing expertise and interest. In our view, the seven research programme lines offer enormous opportunities with the potential for global impact. Each university has adopted one or more programme lines, committing valuable resources in terms of the time, expertise and energy of full professors and talented postdocs.

Citizenship & Democracy

The information revolution has served to inform citizens but has opened wide avenues for misinformation as well, fuelling mistrust and polarisation. With the legitimacy of national and international systems of government being questioned, we can reinvigorate institutions that are vital for democratic compromise, economic prosperity and the rule of law. Digital connectivity can be used to reduce social exclusion and to advance social cohesion and create productive mixtures of national, cultural, and religious identities. These and related societal challenges are addressed in programme line Citizenship & Democracy.

Academics that are working on finding solutions to societal challenges related to Citizenship & Democracy:

MARCEL BROERSMA (UNIVERSITY OF GRONINGEN)

Expertise

Marcel Broersma is full professor of Journalism Studies and Media at the University of Groningen. He is head of the Journalism department and director of the Centre for Media and Journalism Studies. His research interests focus on the transformation of journalism, the innovation and diffusion of forms and styles of journalism, on political communication, and on local and regional journalism. He has published widely on both the history and current development of journalism in the Netherlands and comparatively.

CLAES DE VREESE (UNIVERSITY OF AMSTERDAM)

Expertise

As Professor of political communication, de Vreese is interested in how media and information enable citizens to participate in democratic processes. These opportunities are changing and processes of digitisation change the nature of this. Together with Natali Helberger they lead a large project on the nature and consequences of personalised communication (personalised-communication.net) as a key example of how digitisation can affect media and citizens in a democracy. De Vreese is also the Director of the Digital Communication Methods Lab in which we integrate novel approaches to studying the role of media and communication in a digital world.

NATALI HELBERGER (UNIVERSITY OF AMSTERDAM)

Expertise

Natali Helberger has been appointed professor of Information Law, with a special focus on the use of information, at the University of Amsterdam's (UvA) Faculty of Law. Helberger researches how the role of the user of information is changing under the influence of information technology, and social and economic conditions. She also examines the resulting implications for the legal position, rights and obligations of information users under current and future media and communications law, consumer law and data protection law. Helberger's research features a strong interdisciplinary component: in order to assess whether and how information law ties in with the reality of information users and information markets, she regularly works with communication scientists, social scientists, psychologists as well as cultural scientists and economists.

TON WILTHAGEN (TILBURG UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

The expertise of Wilthagen relates to labour markets, labour market and employment policy, labour relations, labour law and social security: national, international as well as regional. Wilthagen is specifically interested in the relationship between on the one hand labour market dynamism and flexibilization and social cohesion, inclusion, protection and (new) securities on the other. Is a labour market that is both dynamic and inclusive possible at all? What are sustainable labour market policies? One of the key concepts that I developed from this perspective is "flexicurity". Regarding dynamism, Wilthagen also has an interest in how new technologies, such as robotization, influence the labour market and work. Besides research and education (among other things in the Master Labour Law and Employment Relations and the Research Master in Law Tilburg/Leuven) he is strongly engaged in generating societal impact from knowledge and science, as co-leader of the Impact Programme of Tilburg University.

FRANCISKA DE JONG (UTRECHT UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Franciska de Jong is full professor of e-Research for the Humanities and executive director of CLARIN ERIC, the governing body of CLARIN which has its statutory seat at Utrecht University. CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology INfrastructure) has the objective is to provide scholars in the humanities and social sciences seamless access to digital language data and processing tools all across Europe. Currently, her main research interest is in the field of access technology for digital libraries, text mining, cross-language retrieval, the disclosure of cultural heritage collections (in particular spoken audio archives), and e-research at large.

Examples

Report: Automated Decision-Making Fairness in an AI-driven World

Ongoing advances in artificial intelligence are increasingly part of scientific efforts as well as the public debate and the media agenda, raising hopes and concerns about the impact of automated decision-making across different sectors of our society. This report contributes to informing the public debate, providing the results of a survey with 958 participants recruited from high-quality sample of the Dutch population. The report present an overview of public knowledge, perceptions, hopes and concerns about the adoption of AI and ADM across different societal sectors in the Netherlands.

Analyzing the 'life' of newspapers with Machine Learning

Marcel Broersma is Principal Investigator of the collaborative research project NEWSGAC which studies how genres in newspapers and television news can be detected automatically using Machine Learning technology. The project brings together expertise from journalism history scholars, specialists in data modelling, integration and analysis, digital collection experts and eScience Research Engineers.

The Misinformation Crisis

On The Open Mind, University of Amsterdam political communications chair Claes de Vreese discusses global populism and the post-truth present. "We live in an era of information-polution; there is a lot of information out there but it's very hard to verify all of it in a quick manner."

Responsible Data Science

Using data in reliable and responsible ways will be an integral part of any Digital Society research. Promoting responsible data science should limit the potential for misuse of personal data and the risk of undermining public trust. Techniques, methods and tools are needed to safeguard fair, accurate, confidential and transparent (FACT) use of data that is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), and they should be applied universally. These and related societal challenges are addressed in programme line Responsible Data Science.

Academics that are working on finding solutions to societal challenges related to Responsible Data Science:

FRANK VAN HARMELEN (VU AMSTERDAM)

Expertise

Frank van Harmelen is a professor in Knowledge Representation & Reasoning in the Computer Science department (Faculty of Science) at the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. Since 2000, he has played a leading role in the development of the Semantic Web, which aims to make data on the web semantically interpretable by machines through formal representations. He was co-PI on the first European Semantic Web project (OnToKnowledge, 1999), which laid the foundations for the Web Ontology Language OWL. OWL has become a worldwide standard, it is in wide commercial use, and has become the basis for an entire research community. In recent years, he pioneered the development of large scale reasoning engines. He was scientific director of the 10m euro EU-funded Large Knowledge Collider, a platform for distributed computation over semantic graphs with billions of edges. The prize-winning work with his student Jacopo Urbani has improved the state of the art by two orders of magnitude. He is scientific director of The Network Institute. In this interdisciplinary research institute some 150 researchers from the Faculties of Social Science, Humanities and Computer Science collaborate on research topics in computational Social Science and e-Humanities. He is a guest professor at the University of Science and Technology in Wuhan, China.

MICHEL DUMONTIER (MAASTRICHT UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Dumontier is a Distinguished Professor of Data Science at Maastricht University. His research focuses on the development of computational methods for the responsible use and scalable integration of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data and services. His group combines semantic web technologies with machine learning and network analysis for drug discovery and personalized medicine. Dumontier also leads a new inter-faculty Institute of Data Science at Maastricht University whose focus is to bring together science, technology, and social, legal and ethical aspects to strengthen communities, accelerating scientific discovery, and improve health and well-being.

CORIEN PRINS (TILBURG UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Corien Prins is Professor of Law and Information Technology at Tilburg Law School and was president of the Tilburg Institute of Law, Technology, and Society (TILT). Since 2017, she is Chair of the Netherlands Scientific Council for Government Policy (WRR). Since 2009 she has been a member of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW), Chair of the Supervisory Board of Erasmus University Rotterdam and a member of the selection Advisory Committee of the parquet of the Supreme Court.

GEERT-JAN HOUBEN (TU DELFT)

Expertise

As a computer scientist trained in databases, Houben's research has always been involved in how to effectively get meaningful information out of large datasets. Concentrating in particular on large sets of web data, most of his research has focussed on how to attaching meaning to web data, for example for the purpose of enabling web-based information systems to offer user-adapted or personalised information to their users. Being in the centre of data science, this means his research now is devoted to the theory and technology that enables developers and users of data-driven systems to trust the information that the systems provide.

LINNET TAYLOR (TILBURG UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Linnet Taylor is Assistant Professor of Data Ethics, Law and Policy at the Tilburg Institute for Law, Technology, and Society (TILT). Her research focuses on global data justice – the development of a conceptual framework for the ethical and beneficial governance of data technologies based on insights from technology users and providers around the world.

MYKOLA PECHENIZKIY (TU EINDHOVEN)

Expertise

Mykola Pechenizkiy is a Full Professor at the department of Mathematics and Computer Science, Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e), where he holds the Data Mining Chair. His research interests include data science, knowledge discovery and data mining, responsible analytics, including ethics/discrimination-awareness, context-aware predictive analytics, handling concept drift and reoccurring contexts, automation of feature construction and analytics on evolving networks. His core expertise and research interests are in predictive analytics and knowledge discovery from evolving data, and in their application to real-world problems in industry, medicine and education. At the Data Science Center Eindhoven, he leads the Customer Journey interdisciplinary research program aiming at developing techniques for informed and responsible analytics.

Examples

600 Experts in Artificial Intelligence Sign a Letter Calling for European Action

Earlier this year, 600 leading experts in artificial intelligence released a letter calling on European and national leaders to drastically ramp up their support for research excellence and innovation in artificial intelligence (AI).

Five of the scariest predictions about artificial intelligence

As AI comes increasingly closer to maturity, and businesses continue to ramp up investments in it, some worry that not enough attention is being paid to the broader social and moral implications of the technology. CNBC spoke with some experts to see what they think are the five scariest potential future scenarios for AI. "Any computer system, AI or not, that automatically decides on matters of life and death — for example, by launching a missile — is a really scary idea".

The future of data in academia

"Throughout the university, researchers love data and do all kind of interesting things with it", says Michel Dumontier, distinguished professor of Data Science. "Data science is practised in every department and faculty. And yet, even though we share these methods, we barely get to talk to one another."

Health & Well-Being

Digital technology can help promote healthier lifestyles, create healthier environments, optimize detection, diagnosis and treatment of disease and well-being of patients, and advance the quality and efficiency of care, both at home and in institutions. Digital technology should be designed and delivered according to the needs of end users, aimed towards limiting inequalities in access to care. It should help manage the costs of care for populations of all ages. These and related societal challenges are addressed in programme line Health & Well-Being.

Academics that are working on finding solutions to societal challenges related to Health & Well-Being:

ANDREA EVERS (LEIDEN UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Andrea Evers is professor of Health Psychology and chair of the Health-Medical-and-Neuropsychology-Unit at Leiden University. After her PhD (cum laude), Andrea Evers obtained several personal grants for excellent researchers (NWO-Veni 2004, NWO-Vidi 2009, ERC Consolidator Grant 2013, ERC Proof of Concept 2015, NWO-Vici 2017) for her innovative, interdisciplinary and translational research on psychoneurobiological mechanisms and treatments for health and disease. Her research is characterized by a strong interdisciplinary focus, particularly due to connecting Social Sciences with Biomedical and Life Sciences, in addition to collaborations with Neuroscience and Humanities. In addition to her broad clinical and teaching experience, she uniquely combines fundamental and applied science in her translational research, by focusing both on basic research on psychoneurobiology (e.g. stress mechanisms) and translational research on screening and innovative interventions for somatic conditions (e.g. e-health tools). She published more than 200 international and national articles in her research topics.

NATASHA MAURITS (UNIVERSITY OF GRONINGEN)

Expertise

Natasha Maurits is Professor of Clinical Neuroengineering at the University of Groningen. Her interests include Clinical neuroengineering, esp. neurodiagnostics, Multimodal neuroimaging (EEG-EMG-fMRI), computational biofluid dynamics, (r)TMS, biomedical signal analysis.

ANDRÉ DEKKER (MAASTRICHT UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Dekker is a full professor of Clinical Data Science at Maastricht University and lead the GROW-Maastricht University research division of MAASTRO Knowledge Engineering. His research focuses on three main themes: building global data sharing infrastructures; machine learning cancer outcome prediction models from this data; applying outcome prediction models to improve lives of cancer patients. Their scientific breakthrough has been the development of a data sharing and distributed learning infrastructure that does not require data to leave the hospital. This has reduced many of the ethical and other barriers to share health data. They have shown this approach works in more than 20 cancer centres worldwide.

EDITH FESKENS (WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Feskens is Professor in Nutrition and Health over the Lifecourse. The chair group Nutrition and Health over the Lifecourse (within the Division of Human Nutrition and Health) led by Feskens focusses on nutritional needs and interventions to achieve and maintain optimal health throughout the life span. Dietary intake, nutritional status and functional outcomes are studied at the individual level as well as in public health related interventions. Research and training is concentrated on nutrients, foods and dietary patterns, is physiologically oriented and targeted both at western and non-western settings.

AARNOUT BROMBACHER (TU EINDHOVEN)

Expertise

Aarnout Brombacher is Full Professor of Design Theory and Information Flow Analysis. Brombacher has an interest in field-data analysis of complex systems in interaction with users and user communities, data analytics and the resulting customer perceived design quality models. His early career at Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) focused on quality and reliability management, both in the Department of Industrial Design and the Department of Mechanical Engineering. He has extensive experience in industrial quality and reliability improvement projects and developing tools and analysis methods for this field. Later, his interests shifted to sports, activity and human health, using the increasingly available amounts of individual activity data to help create opportunities for more people to become active. He is currently member of the National TopTeam (advisory body of the Dutch government) on Sports and Vitality representing the 14 Dutch universities in this field.

HELEEN RIPER (VU AMSTERDAM)

Expertise

Heleen Riper is Professor of eMental-Health and works at the VU University Amsterdam, GGZ inGeest (Research Department of a large mental health service organization in Amsterdam, the Netherlands) and at the Leuphana University (eMental-Health Research Centre), Lüneburg, Germany. Over the past 15 years her research focus has been on the development of eMental-Health interventions for common mental disorders and substance use disorders, the assessment of their clinical and cost-effectiveness and their implementation in routine practice. In addition, I have studied the requirements and impact of eMental-Health on both national and international health policy-levels. The scope of her current research activities includes the innovative use of mobile health, social media and blended care for the prevention and treatment of common mental disorders. New methodological challenges include the use and evaluation of mobile ecological momentary assessments and interventions, serious gaming for mental health and intelligent reasoning systems for modeling the virtual patient.

HERMIE HERMENS (UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE)

Expertise

Hermens is Professor in Neuromuscular Control at the University of Twente. He was the initiator and coordinator of the SENIAM project, which had a substantial impact as it resulted in a broadly accepted worldwide standard on surface EMG electrodes properties and their placement on the muscles. He was co-founder of Roessingh Research and Development, originating from the Roessingh Rehabilitation Centre, which has grown now in the largest institute in the area of Rehabilitation Technology and Telemedicine in the Netherlands. He was also one of the initiators of the Center for Care Technology Research, where he is now director Technology, being one of the 8 Centres of Research Excellence of the Innovative Medical Devices Initiative. Hermie is coordinating the H2020 project Council of Coaches, focusing on disruptive new way of coaching using multiple artificial coaches and the recently funded Data2person project EDIC (exceptional and deep intelligent coach). He is the coordinator of the UT wide multidisciplinary research program on "Personalised eHealth technology".

MARGRIET SITSKOORN (TILBURG UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Margriet Sitskoorn is a full professor of Clinical Neuropsychology (Department of Cognitive Neuropsychology) at Tilburg University in the Netherlands and is registered as a Clinical Neuropsychologist, Specialist BIG-registration (49050992625). She is the Health & Wellbeing programme leader from Tilburg University's Impact programme. Within the VSNU Digital Society programme Health & Wellbeing, she represents Tilburg University with a specific focus on cognition, personalised care and creating data from both big- and experience data within the field of Health and Wellbeing. Margriet Sitskoorn worked as a clinical neuropsychologist and cognitive scientist at several institutes in the Netherlands and stayed at Henry Ford Hospital Detroit, USA. Sitskoorn has received and continues to be awarded multiple grants from different organisations (e.g. ZonMw, KWF, Fonds Nuts Ohra, Czfonds). She was, amongst others a member of the Dutch Health Council's Special Committee electromagnetic fields, a board member of STT foresight images of the brain, and is a member of the Supervisory board of the Dutch TopSportCommunity of the Netherlands. She also functions as a consulting editor for the peer-reviewed scientific journal Neuropsychology.

LISETTE VAN GEMERT-PIJNEN (UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE)

Expertise

Lisette Van Gemert-Pijnen is Professor of Persuasive Health Technology. The research and tuition conducted by Lisette van Gemert focuses on the design, implementation and evaluation of technology in the healthcare sector with the aim of improving the overall quality of health and safety. The research in particular is oriented towards human-centered and value-driven technology and includes three subthemes: user centered development, persuasive technology design, and business modelling (implementation). Research is part of the Persuasive Health Technology lab, Research center of the Center for eHealth & Wellbeing Research at the University of Twente.

Examples

Inspiring and scientifically proven health advice at 'Healthy University' days

'It's mad,' says Professor of Health Psychology Andrea Evers. Our scientists as medics and psychologists are telling patients how to live healthier lives, and our students are developing treatment plans for all kinds of target groups as part of their study programme. But this knowledge isn't being used within the university, and that while staff and students are just as likely as others in society to suffer from a chronic illness arising from genetic misfortune or an unhealthy lifestyle.

Enabling remote of cognitive behaviour through mobile experience sampling

Cognitive decline is among the normal processes of ageing, involving problems with memory, language, thinking and judgment, happening at different times and affecting people's live to a significant extent. Traditional clinical methods for cognitive assessment are conducted by experts once first symptoms appear. Mobile technologies can help supporting more immediate, continuous and ubiquitous measurements, thus potentially allowing for much earlier diagnosis of cognitive disorders.

Smart Machines To Empower Oncology Docs and Patients

Machines cannot satisfy the inherently human function of physicians in health care; they cannot interact adequately with patients, said Andre Dekker. But artificial intelligence can provide the tools that will make this interaction more beneficial, he told a standing-room-only crowd of hundreds who attended the talks about AI. "AI will allow us to share decision-making," said Dekker, medical physicist and head of knowledge engineering at the MAASTRO clinic and professor at Maastricht University.

Learning & Education

Continuing technological change will both enable and require new types of learning and communication, not just during childhood but throughout people's lives. More than ever, people of all ages should be enabled to continuously update their skills to engage with the environment and the rest of the world. Formal and informal learning processes should be personalized and made more effective. These and related societal challenges are addressed in programme line Learning & Education.

Academics that are working on finding solutions to societal challenges related to Learning & Education:

HAROLD BEKKERING (RADBOD UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Harold Bekkering is Professor of Cognitive Psychology at the Donders Institute for Brain, Cognition and Behaviour of the Radboud University Nijmegen. His research has covered many different ways of learning ranging from basic sensorimotor learning to complex forms of social learning. Lately, he aims to implement knowledge about human learning in educational settings.

MARCUS SPECHT (OPEN UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

With his background in psychology and engineering, Specht has always been researching the interaction between humans and technology. Empowering humans with technology to learn more efficient, effective or by having fun and enjoying themselves while learning is the big challenge for the next hundred years of digital education. He has approached new opportunities from a design-based reach perspective and developed new technology applications for education and he also evaluated technology for enabling better human learning. Beside empowering more efficient human learning also the impact of technology on processes as information distribution, educational monitoring and formative assessment, and development of educational material has been part of his research.

MAX LOUWERSE (TILBURG UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Max Louwerse is Professor Cognitive Psychology and Artificial Intelligence in the Department of Cognitive Science & Artificial Intelligence at Tilburg University. He received his PhD in Linguistics (University of Edinburgh) and worked at the University of Memphis as Full Professor in the Department of Psychology and the Institute for Intelligent Systems, where he also worked as Director. Louwerse published over 120 articles in journals, proceedings and books in cognitive science, computational linguistics, and psycholinguistics (text and discourse, multimodal communication, embodied cognition, medical informatics, and spatio-temporal models) and holds two patents. Louwerse was founder of the DAF Technology Lab, the virtual and mixed reality lab on the Tilburg University campus, was involved in setting up the Jheronimus Academy of Data Science (www.jads.nl) and is co-founder of Mind Labs (www.mind-labs.eu).

Examples

Inspiring and scientifically proven health advice at 'Healthy University' days

Doing things together – nothing is more natural for Homo Sapiens. We are highly social animals. Professor Harold Bekkering and his Action and Neuro-cognition Group are trying to unravel the complex processes that underlie human cooperation.

Let's Innovate our Education

According to Max Louwerse, the typical way of education at universities is not from this time anymore. That is why he thinks that classrooms should be complemented with technology in order to make classes more interactive. With this technology it will be possible to make use of virtual, augmented and mixed reality to eventually create better education.

Time will tell: The role of mobile learning analytics in self-regulated learning

This longitudinal study explores the effects of tracking and monitoring time devoted to learn with a mobile tool, on self-regulated learning. Graduate students (n = 36) from three different online courses used their own mobile devices to track how much time they devoted to learn over a period of four months.

Work & Organisations

Digital technology disrupts markets for products, services and jobs. In manufacturing, intensive use of data and 3D printing could transform value and production chains and bring us closer to a more circular economy. Automation, robotics and artificial intelligence can revolutionise major industries (including logistics, retail and white-collar professions). That could also require new ways to balance education, work, free time and retirement, and new strategies nets to prevent social inequalities and societal exclusion. These and related societal challenges are addressed in programme line Work & Organisations.

Academics that are working on finding solutions to societal challenges related to Work & Organisations:

TANJA VAN DER LIPPE (UTRECHT UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Tanja van der Lippe is Professor of Sociology of Households and Employment Relations at the Department of Sociology and Research School (ICS) of Utrecht University, head of the Department of Sociology and research director ICS Utrecht. Her research interests are in the area of work-family linkages in Dutch and other societies, for which she received a number of large scale grants from Dutch and European Science Foundations. She is an elected member of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW, 2014), and of the Royal Holland Society of Sciences and Humanities (KHMW, 2013). She has published extensively on work and care of men and women, time use and time pressure in a comparative way, and the position of men and women on the labor market (including supervisory positions) in Western and Eastern European countries.

MARLEEN HUYSMAN (VU AMSTERDAM)

Expertise

Huysman is professor at the School of Business and Economics (SBE) at the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. In her research she studies the, often unintended, consequences of digital technologies for how we work and organise. Huysman studies the socio-technical practices to understand how our traditional ideas about organising work are challenged in our digital society. A hallmark of the research at her group (KIN Centre for Digital Innovation) is that they create understanding of the development and use of digital technologies by studying these processes in practice, working in close collaboration with organisations.

Examples

The concepts of busyness and balance in a society where institutions are shifting

“‘Busy, busy, busy’. This, I’m sure, is a feeling familiar to us all. We are living in a society where it seems time waits for no one, and we’re switched on all the time, everywhere. And for some of us it poses quite a challenge, whilst sitting here in the Dom Church, not to briefly rove in other worlds, glance at our iPhones, check the latest headlines, read our newest emails.”

The ‘onlooker effect’: how bystanders influence our use of digital technologies

The use of mobile devices has permeated our daily lives and has in various ways influenced the way we interact with each other. For instance, even during an animated conversation with a loved one we allow ourselves to be disturbed by intruding push messages on our phone. In work meetings we often switch between screens on our laptop to check emails or multitask. And although we know we need an eye on safety in traffic we regularly prioritize texting while crossing the streets. How did we get this ‘addicted’ to our mobile devices? Why do we seem to have developed norms that allow ourselves to be so distracted by technology?

Research on Digital Innovation

KIN is all about Digital Innovation. KIN is fascinated by the ways in which the use and development of digital innovations affect the way we work and organize. Their mission is to make the world a better place in the digital era: they bring together academia and practice to truly understand the social and long-term consequences of digital innovations in organizations.

Digital Cities & Communities

Digital technology can help to create infrastructure with which to manage urbanisation, population growth, mobility, effects of climate change and transition to greater sustainability. By 'monitoring citizens' behaviour, smart cities could optimize urban planning and transport, and utility and community services such as waste collection and law enforcement. Smart cities should provide their own citizens safety and liveability, and interact optimally with surrounding rural communities. These and related societal challenges are addressed in programme line Digital Cities & Communities.

Academics that are working on finding solutions to societal challenges related to Digital Cities & Communities:

LIESBET VAN ZOONEN (ERASMUS UNIVERSITY ROTTERDAM)

Expertise

Van Zoonen is academic director of the Leiden-Delft-Erasmus Centre for Big Open and Linked Data (BOLD) Cities. Their agenda concerns the responsible application of data science for public values and the public good in urban environments. This involves anything from smart mobility solutions to data driven benefit systems. As a matter of principle, they collaborate with local government, creative professionals and citizen groups. They designed the SHARED values as a criterion for human centred information technology, and use this in their own research to assess if and how data science projects in the city serve the benefits of the city and its citizens.

FRITS CLAASSEN (WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH)

Expertise

Frits Claassen is Associate Professor at the Operations Research and Logistics Group. My research aims to contribute particularly to the applicability of Operations Research (OR) models – and solution techniques in practice. My general research objective is to combine the strong elements of normative OR models (i.e. what practice ought to do) with descriptive decision-making (i.e. what practice actually does), such that models and solution approaches arise that provide for insights in what practice should, and actually can do.

Examples

Gamified survey questions citizens about digital traces in public spaces

Smart lampposts, vehicle detector loops in the road, public Wi-Fi in the city centre and car parks that read your number plate: our living environment is becoming increasingly driven by modern digital technologies and vast data streams used to monitor, manage and improve the infrastructure and public services in the city. The Leiden-Delft-Erasmus Centre for BOLD Cities aims to make people aware of these data points, in part by means of a new game: 'Your neighbourhood - Your data'.

Research of the Operations Research and Logistics Group

The research projects focus on decision making in the domain of agrifood and biobased supply chain. Central in these projects is the increasing complexity and uncertainty, as well as the specific characteristics of our domain. Our work supports organisations in achieving robust performance, including the trade-offs between costs, service, quality and sustainability.

Leiden-Delft-Erasmus news reports on 'The Ethics of Big Data' seminar

When the decision is finally taken to utilise data to resolve issues or improve services, fundamental questions will remain on the subject of ethics and privacy. Who actually owns the data? How can we ensure that security and privacy are safeguarded? How can we involve the people whose data is used?

Safety & Security

Digital technology provides opportunities and challenges for human and data safety. War, peacekeeping and law enforcement will increasingly involve all sorts of data connections; government surveillance should balance reducing threats with preserving privacy and other civil liberties. Public and private organizations storing personal data require better protection against data intrusions. Vital institutions' data require more robust shielding from saboteurs. Reliable, secure, high-capacity, energy-efficient data transfer and storage technologies are urgently needed. These and related societal challenges are addressed in programme line Safety & Security.

Academics that are working on finding solutions to societal challenges related to Safety & Security:

HERBERT BOS (VU AMSTERDAM)

Expertise

Herbert Bos is full professor at the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam and leads the VUsec Systems Security research group. He obtained an ERC Starting Grant to work on reverse engineering and an NWO VICI grant to work on vulnerability detection. These and other systems security topics are still close to his heart. Other research interests include OS design, networking, and dependable systems. Herbert moved to The Netherlands after approximately four years at the Universiteit Leiden. Before that he obtained his Ph.D. from the Cambridge University Computer Laboratory, followed by a brief stint at KPN Research (now TNO Telecom).

MICHEL VAN EETEN (TU DELFT)

Expertise

Professor of Public Administration, in particular the governance of infrastructures in the Policy, Organisation, Law and Gaming section. I am also the director of the TPM Graduate School, which is currently being set up. My current research focuses on a variety of topics, most notably the governance of infrastructures, internet security, high reliability organizations, and multi-actor networks. I lecture about these and other topics at Delft University of Technology and at the Netherlands School of Public Administration in The Hague, an institute providing executive education for Dutch public sector officials.

BART JACOBS (RADBOD UNIVERSITY)

Expertise

Professor of Software Security and Correctness, Digital Security Group, Institute for Computing and Information Sciences, Radboud University Nijmegen. My research concentrates on theoretical and practical aspects of security. On the theoretical side, my focus is on quantum logic and probabilistic computation, supported by an ERC Advanced Grant, see also the EfProb Python library for probabilistic computation. On the practical side, I'm interested in identity and privacy management, see eg. the IRMA project and video on attribute-based authentication, in security and privacy in personalised medicine (see the PEP technology), and in cyber security and intelligence and the broader societal aspects of computer security.

Examples

A body armour for software

"I was walking from the railway station to the VU campus, deep in thought about a problem a colleague was having. Then it struck me: I needed to view the problem from a totally different angle." A new method for securing computer programs against cybercrime was born, to help prevent attacks such as the recent hacks on KPN, LinkedIn, banks and governments." Herbert Bos, Professor of Systems and Network Security, is developing systems to protect software against cyberthieves and other criminals.

The debate on Cybercrime

'For every dollar in the pocket of a cybercriminal, we spend sometimes 1,000 or even 10,000 dollars at preventing that crime, that money would be much better spend at catching and prosecuting the criminals', says Michel van Eeten, Professor of Governance of Cybersecurity.

Bart Jacobs puts digital security on the agenda

Jacobs not only highlights errors that make software vulnerable – he also shows how software can be made more secure. One example of this is the improved version of the anonymous 'OV' (public transport) chip card that came into use in 2011. Radboud Computer scientists helped to make it, after having pointed out the weak points of an earlier design a few years earlier. Similarly, Jacob's group made a super-secure chip for the DigiD identification card in 2013.

Digital Society

VSNU

vereniging van universiteiten
association of universities
THE NETHERLANDS

The challenges
of a digital society

